

GEOMETRIK MASALALARNI YECHISHDA AKADEMIK LITSEY O'QUVCHILARNI IJODIY QOBILIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

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O.U.Pulatov

N.N.Tursunov

P.M.Rayimqulov

Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti akademik litsey

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Planimetriya kursidagi ba'zi masalalarni yechishda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatlarini rivojlantirishning ba'zi jihatlari qaraladi va o'rganilayotgan har bir usulni geometriyani o'qitishda qo'llash bo'yicha kokret misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Uchburchak medianasi, balandlik, sistema, yuza, sinuslar teoremasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются некоторые аспекты развития творческой активности учащихся при решении некоторых задач курса «Планиметрия», приводятся конкретные примеры того, как каждый изучаемый метод может быть использован в обучении геометрии.

Ключевые слова: медиана треугольника, высота, система, поверхность, теорема синусов.

Annotation: This article discusses some aspects of developing students' creative activity in solving some of the problems in the Planimetry course, and provides specific examples of how each method studied can be used in teaching geometry.

Keywords: Triangle median, altitude, system, surface, math sine theorem.

Planimetriya kursini yakuniy takrorlashda tayanch masalalar sistemasini keltiramiz

1.Uchburchak medianalari xossasi.

1. Uchburchak medianalari bir nuqtada kesishadi va unda uchidan hisoblaganda 2:1 nisbatda bo'linadi.

2. Mediana uchburchakni ikkita teng uchburchakka ajratadi.

2.1-rasm

Isbot. BM – $\triangle ABC$ ning medianasi bo'lsin. $\triangle ABM$, $\triangle MBC$ uchburchaklarni qaraymiz (2.1-rasm).

$\triangle ABM$ va $\triangle MBC$ uchburchaklar uchun BH – balandlik umumiy bo'lganligi uchun, u holda

$$S_{\triangle ABM} = \frac{1}{2} AM \cdot BH; \quad S_{\triangle MBC} = \frac{1}{2} MC \cdot BH$$

Shartga ko'ra BM – mediana $\Rightarrow AM=MC \Rightarrow S_{\triangle ABM} = S_{\triangle MBC}$.

3. Uchburchak medianalari uni oltita teng uchburchakka ajratadi
 $S_{ABC}=3S_{AOB}=3S_{BOC}=3S_{COA}$.

2.2-rasm

Isbot. BK , CM , AN – $\triangle ABC$ ning medianalari bo'lsin, ular O nuqtada kesishadi (2.2-rasm). $\triangle AOB$, $\triangle BOC$, $\triangle AOC$ uchburchak hosil bo'ladi. Ularning yuzalari mos ravishda S_1 , S_2 , S_3 larga teng bo'lsin. $\triangle ABC$ ning yuzi esa S ga teng bo'lsin.

$\triangle ABK$ va $\triangle CBK$ uchburchaklarni qaraymiz – ular teng yuzalarga ega, chunki BK – mediana.

$\triangle AOC$ uchburchakda OK – mediana, demak, $S_{\triangle AOK} = S_{\triangle COK}$.

Bundan $S_2=S_3$, $S_3=S_1$, $S_{ABC}=3S_{AOB}=3S_{BOC}=3S_{COA}$

$\triangle MOB$, $\triangle BON$, $\triangle NOC$, $\triangle COK$, $\triangle KOA$ va $\triangle AOM$ uchburchaklarning yuzalarini mos ravishda S_1 , S_2 , S_3 , S_4 , S_5 , S_6 deb belgilaymiz.

$\triangle AOB$, $\triangle BOC$, $\triangle AOC$ uchburchaklar yuzalari teng va $\triangle AOM$, $\triangle BOM$ uchburchaklar yuzalari teng, demak, $S_1 = S_6$. Shunga o'xshash $S_2 = S_3$.

Agar $S_1+S_6= S_2+S_3$ va $2S_2=2S_1$ bo'lsa, demak, $S_2=S_1$. va h.k. Barcha olita uchburchak teng yuzalarga ega va ular $\triangle ABC$ uchburchak yuzasining oltidan birini tashkil etadi.

Sistemaning masalalari:

1-masala. Uchburchakning ikki tomoni mos ravishda 6 va 8 ga teng. Bu tomonlarga o'tkazilgan medianalar o'zaro perpendikulyar. Uchburchak yuzasini toping.

Yechish.

2.3-rasm.

$AB=6$, $AC=8$ bo'lsin (2.3-rasm).

U holda CC_1 va BB_1 medianalar o'zaro perpendikulyar va O nuqtada kesishadi. $S_{ABC}=3S_{BOC}$, $S_{BOC}=\frac{1}{2}OB \cdot OC$, chunki BOC uchburchak to'g'ri burchakli.

Agar $BB_1=3x$ bo'lsa, u holda $OB=2x$; agar $OC_1=y$, bo'lsa, u holda $OC=2y$. BOC_1 va COB_1 uchburchaklar to'g'ri burchakli va Pifagor teoremasiga ko'ra

$$\begin{cases} x^2 + 4y^2 = 16 \\ 4x^2 + y^2 = 9 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} x = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \\ y = \sqrt{\frac{11}{3}} \end{cases} \quad S_{BOC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{4}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot \frac{2\sqrt{11}}{\sqrt{3}} = \frac{4\sqrt{11}}{3}$$

U holda $S_{ABC} = 3 \cdot \frac{4\sqrt{11}}{3} = 4\sqrt{11}$

Javob: $4\sqrt{11}$.

2-masala. ABC uchburchakda AA_1 va CC_1 – medianalar, bunda $AA_1=5$, $\angle CAA_1 = \frac{\pi}{8}$, $\angle ACC_1 = \frac{\pi}{4}$. ABC uchburchak yuzasini toping.

U holda

$$S_{AOC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot AO \cdot OC \cdot \sin \angle AOC, \quad S_{AOC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot AO \cdot OC \cdot \sin \angle AOC,$$

$$S_{AOC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{10}{3} \cdot \frac{10}{3} \cdot \frac{\sin \frac{\pi}{8}}{\sin \frac{\pi}{4}} \cdot \sin \frac{5\pi}{8}, S_{AOC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{10}{3} \cdot \frac{10}{3} \cdot \frac{\sin \frac{\pi}{8}}{\sin \frac{\pi}{4}} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi}{8} = \frac{25}{9}.$$

Yechish.

2.4-rasm.

$$S_{ABC} = 3S_{AOC} \cdot AO = \frac{10}{3}.$$

OC tomon uzunligini sinuslar teoremasidan topamiz:

$$\frac{AO}{\sin \frac{\pi}{4}} = \frac{OC}{\sin \frac{\pi}{8}} \Rightarrow OC = \frac{10}{3} \cdot \frac{\sin \frac{\pi}{8}}{\sin \frac{\pi}{4}}.$$

Javob: $\frac{25}{3}$.

3-masala. Uchburchak medianalari uzunliklari 3, 4 va 5 ga teng. Uchburchak yuzini toping.

2.5-rasm.

Yechish. A_1, B_1, C_1 – mos ravishda BC, AC va AB tomonlarning o'rtalari (2.5-rasm). $AA_1 = 3, BB_1 = 4, CC_1 = 5$ bo'lsin. U holda masalaga ko'ra $AO = 2, CO = \frac{10}{3}, B_1O = \frac{4}{3}$ va $S_{ABC} = 3S_{AOC}$. AOC uchburchakni parallelogrammgacha to'ldiramiz, BB_1 to'g'ri chiziqda B_1 nuqtadan B_1O ga teng B_1D kesmani qo'yamiz.

$$\text{U holda } S_{AOC} = S_{AOD} = \frac{1}{2} S_{A OCD}.$$

$$S_{AOD} = \sqrt{4 \cdot 2 \cdot \left(4 - \frac{10}{3}\right) \cdot \left(4 - \frac{8}{3}\right)} = \frac{8}{3}. \text{ Demak, } S_{ABC} = 8.$$

Javob: $S_{ABC} = 8$

4-masala. Uchburchakning ikki tomoni uzunliklari 27 va 29 ga teng. Uchinchi tomoniga o'tkazilgan mediana uzunligi 26 ga teng. Uzunligi 27 ga teng bo'lgan tomonga o'tkazilgan balandlikni toping.

2.6-rasm

yechish. $AB=29, AC=27$ bo'lsin, mediana $AA_1=26$ (2.6-rasm).

BN balandlikni topish uchun ABC uchburchak yuzasini bilish yetarli. ABC uchburchak yuzasini topish uchun uning AA_1 medianasini davom ettirib $ABKC$ parallelogrammgacha to'ldiramiz. U holda $S_{ABC} = S_{ABK} = \frac{1}{2} S_{ABKC}$.

$$S_{ABK} = \sqrt{54 \cdot 27 \cdot 2 \cdot 25} = 270. \quad S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} AC \cdot BH, \quad 270 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 27 \cdot BH, \quad BH = 20.$$

Javob: 20.

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